

THE MECHANISM OF DETERMINING THE LEVEL OF INTELLECTUAL ABILITY (IQ) FOR THE ADMINISTRATIVE ACTIVITY OF THE HEAD OF A PRESCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANIZATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11083195>

Abstract: In this article, the mechanism for determining the level of intellectual ability (IQ) of the head of a preschool educational organization is presented.

Key words: intellectual, technology, innovation, creativity, coefficient, non-standard, awareness

It is known that some people are good at science and some people are good at humanities. Again, we have observed that an artist of superior talent becomes overwhelmed by simple mathematical examples, and a brilliant mathematician with less artistic ability. Can we call such people intelligent? According to Spearman, humans have a general intelligence. In his opinion, people have their own special abilities that separate them from each other. Spearman developed factor analysis, a statistical procedure. He explained the temporary connections of related elements. According to Spearman, the total sum of competence depends on our mental attitude.

Satoshi Kanazawa (2004) see general intelligence as a type of intelligence. General intelligence helps us solve problems in everyday life.

By the 1980s, there was a comparison of Spiremennig's theory of single intelligence and Thurstone's theories of academic abilities. According to them, if a person succeeds in one cognitive domain, then he will achieve similar victories in other domains as well. The main factor in adaptation to life is not the general intelligence of the individual, but the ability to interact with each other over time. H. Gardner considered intelligence as a sum of several abilities. He conducted his research on people with low abilities. He believed that brain damage can extinguish one ability but leave the rest.

Gardner conducted his research on subjects with physiological damage to certain parts of the brain. They often have lower scores on intelligence tests. Some of the representatives of this syndrome have not developed speech. But they had the ability to calculate addition and subtraction as quickly as an electronic calculator. Some have memorized the dates associated with a historical day. Owners of this syndrome were able to achieve success even in artistic creation.

R. Shtenbegr, R. Wagner agreed with Gardner's idea, but analyzed the presence of 3 different factors of intelligence in a person:

The presence of akademic competence in solving the problem. Such skills are assessed by marking the single correct answer in mental tests

Practical intelligence helps to choose the most convenient solution to problems in everyday life in order to adapt to the environment.

Creative mind. Representatives of this type are distinguished by their reaction in unfamiliar situations.

The problem of creativity, which is a higher form of independent thinking, has been studied very deeply in foreign psychology, which is mainly interpreted as the ability to be creative. The reason we do not use this definition as "creative" ("*create*" means "to create"), we used the term "creativity" to avoid the impression that creativity is a high level of intellectual activity. The problem of creativity in psychology has been consistently studied since the 1950s. But in our research, we tentatively called the term "creativity" in Uzbek as "mental creativity" and found it necessary to study it as a psychological basis of independent thinking. Thus, from now on, when thinking about mental creativity, non-standard thinking, its independence and "creativity" are meant.

The breakup of creativity was motivated by the lack of correlation between traditional intelligence tests and problem-solving success. This quality essentially means that it depends on the ability to use the information provided by the mind, the quick method and various methods in solving the tasks.

By analyzing the definitions of creativity, they can be divided into 6 types: *gestalt* definition (the creative process is defined as breaking existing *gestalts* and creating a better one), *innovative (new)* definition (according to the novelty of the final result oriented to the evaluation of creativity), *aesthetic or expressive* (emphasizing the self-expression of the creator), *psychoanalytic* (creativity is defined as the interaction between "He", "I" and "Ideal - I" 'reefing'); *problematic* (which defines creativity as a problem-solving process. It can also incorporate *JP Guilford* 's definition that "Creativity is a process of divergent abilities"), the sixth type can include various definitions that do not belong to any of the types described above (for example, replenishing the stock of "universal" knowledge)

It is difficult to assess the content, essence and structure of definitions related to the term of creativity collected in the present period. According to the researchers, "the very understanding of what creativity is requires creative action. One of the authors of recent studies defines creativity as the achievement of something significant and new, that is, "in other words, it is the effort of people to change the world."

Thus, the relationship between the creative process and the level of intelligence affects the personal characteristics of students and their adaptation methods.

According to Stenberg and Gardner, several abilities can make a person lucky.

One of the criteria of creativity is *non-standard*. As EPTorrance points out, unique and original answers are not necessarily necessarily the same. Often, there is an unjustified confusion of concepts: creative ability is considered the same as non-standard, non-standard is interpreted as originality, and originality is interpreted as the same as unique answers in the test group. Non-standard is a broader concept than originality.

The second criterion is *awareness*. In this context, it is assumed that the examinee has understood the solution to the problem.

Intelligence tests require convergent thinking from the individual. And creative tests require divergent thinking.

Creativity is the ability to create new and valuable ideas at the same time.

Sternberg and his colleagues developed 5 components of creativity.

1. Diversity of knowledge in a person. The knowledge we gained was considered the basis of many of our ideas. The more worldly knowledge we have, the more blocks there are

in our psyche. The more knowledge we have in solving problems in life, the easier it is to solve them.

2. Imaginative thinking allows to see things and events anew, to recreate and connect them. By imagining the main element of the problem, we master it and take it to a new level.

3. Risk-taking - search for new impressions. This can be seen in two ways. That is, the first one can be seen as a **determination** to overcome **risk and problem**. Individuals with this characteristic prefer to have a new experience than to go back.

4. Intrinsic motivation creates a sense of interest and satisfaction in solving a complex problem in a person rather than compulsion. A creative person does not think about the duration of the issue, the income it generates and the applicants. The focus is on the satisfaction and motivation of solving the problem. When Isaac Newton was asked, "How do you solve such complex problems," he replied, "I have been thinking about this problem all day and night."

5. A creative environment helps to support creative ideas in a person. A positive relationship with colleagues and their support motivates the development of ideas in a person. However, it should be noted that some studies have also observed negative effects of the social environment on the individual. For example, American students are given an essay writing task. They were warned in advance that the essay they wrote would be checked by their fellow students. The other group was only told to write an essay. The results showed that the warned group's essays were known to be poorly written. In this case, we can clearly see the negative influence of the social environment on creativity.

In conclusion, we can say that both heredity and environment play an important role in the formation of mental abilities. In the early stages of human development, genetic factors seem to be more dominant. But over the years, the environment has its influence on the development of mental abilities. Its further development or fading depends on the environment.

In conclusion, we can say that when we say the word intelligence, we mean measuring it through tests. But how true these theories are. To what extent can we trust them? We can observe that the questions of this type of tests do not take into account the living conditions of representatives of all strata. Even Alfred Bine mentioned the need to work on the analysis of the intelligence tests he invented. The reason is that the results of these tests are far from the truth. In addition, such tests are aimed at researching only one aspect of intelligence. It has been observed that people with highly developed emotional and practical intelligence do not perform well in these tests. However, today the IQ coefficient has not lost its significance.

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